

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

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Abstract

This document provides an overview of the activities undertaken to design, organise, and implement the CLS INFRA Transnational Access (TNA) Fellowship Programme. Over the course of the project, six calls were launched, from November 2021 to November 2024, and a total of 51 visits were carried out across seven partner institutions.

In particular, the report provides comprehensive information on the management of the Programme, including details on eligibility rules, evaluation procedures, communication and dissemination activities, and a summary of all the projects that were carried out. Key statistics on gender balance, geographical coverage, career levels, and success rates are also presented. Finally, this deliverable offers some insights into the value and impact of the TNA Fellowship Programme.

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1. Introduction

The overall aim of **CLS INFRA**¹, an Integrating Activities for Starting Communities (IASC) project, was to create unified and easy access to the best European and national infrastructures for the CLS community, which had not been fully supported to benefit from the existing infrastructures and data resources.

The project therefore aimed to consolidate, integrate, and further develop institutional, national, and regional efforts to build shared and sustainable access to high-quality data, tools, and knowledge in the field of literary studies in general, and Computational Literary Studies (CLS) in particular. CLS INFRA used a balanced set of Networking, Joint Research, and Transnational Access activities to instigate the transformation of the CLS community from one based on informal exchanges of knowledge and resources to one based on a shared infrastructure, while at the same time creating the necessary conditions for the wider adoption of digital technologies in traditional literary studies and other related disciplines.

One of the major activities of the project was the organisation of transnational calls, enabling researchers to gain knowledge and expertise through close contact with experts at hosting institutions. Transnational Access (TNA) activities within the project were designed to help bridge the gaps between lesser-resourced and better-resourced communities.

Seven project partner institutions² provided access to a wide range of data, tools, and knowledge. Scholars from literary studies, or those with an interest in Computational Literary Studies methods, were invited to apply for a fellowship grant for a suggested duration of 4 to 12 weeks, depending on the host institution. Shorter visits, however, were also taken into consideration.

Successful applicants had the opportunity to:

- Interact with experts;
- Receive advice on ongoing projects;
- Learn how to use the ecosystem of data, tools and standards;
- Assemble new literary corpora;
- Profit from hands-on training and support.

During the course of the project, a total of six calls were launched, resulting in 51 accepted projects out of 108 applications.

¹ Project description on CORDIS: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101004984>. DOI: [10.3030/101004984](https://doi.org/10.3030/101004984).

² University of Potsdam, the Austrian Academy of Sciences, UNED, Charles University, Ghent University, Trier University and the University of Galway.

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Although the participating institutions were not able to deliver all 372 planned units of access (with one unit equal to one week of access, and 333 weeks awarded in total), the programme was nonetheless considered successful, given that the number of supported projects was significantly higher than expected.

The CLS INFRA Transnational Access (TNA) Fellowship Programme was implemented by Work Package 9, which was composed by the following project partners: DARIAH ERIC (lead), IJP PAN, University of Potsdam, the Austrian Academy of Sciences, UNED, Charles University, Ghent University, Trier University and the University of Galway.

Apart from the support and hosting provided by the participating institutions, the work was divided into two management tasks:

T9.1 – Management and Oversight of the TNA Selection Process:

This task ensured an accountable and transparent approach to the selection and appointment of Transnational Access (TNA) Fellows. It worked closely with the TNA hosts, Work Package 1 (Management, Coordination and Innovation Planning), and Work Package 2 (Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation) to disseminate calls, collect applications, distribute them for evaluation, and act as a central point of contact for applicants throughout the TNA application process.

T9.2 – Recruitment and Administration of the Activities of the External Advisory Board:

This task coordinated the appointment of, and managed communications with, the CLS INFRA External Advisory Board, whose expertise was crucial for evaluating and selecting projects.

This deliverable summarises all phases of the work, from its design to implementation, and provides information on its impact and legacy.

Section 2 provides information on the design and implementation phases, explaining in detail the offering, the modalities for participation and application submission, the application procedure, accessibility rules, and how the evaluations were carried out.

The third section describes in detail the communication and dissemination procedures implemented to raise awareness about the TNA Fellowship programme, as well as the channels used to maximise its impact.

Section 4 presents the list of all accepted projects, including the name of the fellowship grant holder, their institution of affiliation, the host institution, the project title, and the visit duration.

The fifth section highlights key statistics, including the units of access offered, gender balance, geographical coverage, success rates, and the career levels of both successful and unsuccessful applicants.

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The last section provides information on the overall impact, based on data gathered from a survey conducted toward the end of the project and from project activity reports. It also describes parallel initiatives carried out during the six-month extension from March to August 2025.

Finally, Annex I presents all the project abstracts, while Annex II lists the resources made available following the visits.

2. TNA implementation

2.1 CLS Fellowship Programme

The CLS INFRA Fellowship Programme was designed to offer scholars access to a broad array of data, tools, and expertise. It welcomed applications from researchers in literary studies or those with an interest in Computational Literary Studies methods. Fellowship grants were hosted by participating infrastructure providers, giving successful applicants not only free physical access to these facilities but also the opportunity to become part of the wider CLS community. By applying to one of the open calls, fellows had the chance to:

- Interact with experts;
- Receive advice on ongoing projects;
- Learn how to use the ecosystem of data, tools, and standards;
- Assemble new literary corpora;
- Benefit from hands-on training and support.

Successful applicants were expected to spend between 4 and 12 weeks at the host institution, although shorter stays were also possible.

2.2 Research institutions offering access

Out of the 14 beneficiaries participating in the CLS INFRA project, 7 institutions provided access to their research infrastructure:

1. Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities, Ghent University, Belgium;
2. Moore Institute for Research in the Humanities and Social Studies, University of Galway, Ireland;
3. Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), Austrian Academy of Sciences (OEAW), Austria;
4. Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics, Institute of the Czech National Corpus, Charles University, Czech Republic;
5. Network for Digital Humanities at the University of Potsdam, Germany;
6. Trier Center for Digital Humanities (TCDH) at Trier University, Germany;
7. Laboratorio de Innovación en Humanidades Digitales (LINHD), UNED, Spain.

Each of these institutions planned to offer the following units of access, where one unit represents one week:

Name of the institution	Planned units of access	Estimated number of projects
Ghent University	36	3
University of Galway	48	6

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Austrian Academy of Sciences	72	6
Charles University	72	6
University of Potsdam	24	3
Trier University	48	6
UNED	72	6

In total, 372 units of access were planned, an ambitious target, considering the scale of the project, with an estimated number of 36 projects overall.

Each research institution was asked to prepare a one-page document briefly describing the institution, the existing tools, services, and expertise available, as well as a paragraph detailing the expected aim of the fellowship. This document also included contact information, as it was strongly recommended during the calls to reach out to potential host institutions to ensure that the project aligned with their knowledge and expertise, and that meaningful support could be effectively provided. In most cases, applicants were able to restructure their project proposals to better align with the expertise available at the host institutions. Furthermore, this alignment was one of the selection criteria.

In some cases, these documents were slightly adapted from call to call to refine the expected aim of the fellowship. Below is an example of the documents introducing the participating research institutions, which were made available on the CLS INFRA TNA dedicated website.

Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities, Ghent University, Belgium

Visiting fellowship contact
Julie M. Birkholz
Julie.Birkholz@ugent.be
GhentCDH, Ghent University
<http://www.ghentcdh.ugent.be/>

The Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities (GhentCDH) is an interdisciplinary research centre facilitating digitally-enabled research in the Arts and Humanities at Ghent University & beyond. GhentCDH offers advice & guidance to Ghent University researchers throughout the research project lifecycle where digital tools, methods or collections are used, with a specific focus on digital text analysis, collaborative databases and geospatial analysis. GhentCDH is also the co-partner in the Royal Library of Belgium's Digital Research Lab, which facilitates the digital access of KBR's diverse digitised and born-digital collections to stimulate the (re)use of these digital sources, data and metadata of the collections with research as a core driver. The GhentCDH leads the development of the CLARIAH Open Humanities Service Infrastructure offering a sustainable portfolio of services enabling digital scholarship in the arts and humanities.

Existing tools, services and expertise

Services currently offered by the infrastructure:
The core services we offer are:

- Digital text analysis: support and information to researchers regarding digital text analysis. We offer advice on corpus building, working with digital text analysis tools, and using computer-assisted qualitative data analysis.
- Via the KBR's Digital Research Lab, GhentCDH can offer unique access to select digitised and born-digital collections of the Royal Library of Belgium.
- Collaborative databases: advice and support for using collaborative research databases. We help researchers to develop a database instance, for example powered by e.g. [Nodeggol](#). We provide advice regarding data standards and linked data.
- DH advice: advice and guidance throughout the research project lifecycle where digital tools, methods or collections are used. For the research data management and training we work closely with the Library Lab of the Faculty of Arts and Philosophy Library.

Aim of the fellowship

In this round we will be able to welcome one research fellow that proposes work in named entity recognition, sentiment analysis and/or specifically aspect based sentiment analysis for literary texts in English, French, German or Dutch. The Computational Literary Studies (CLS) fellowship at GhentCDH is primarily directed towards: a) humanities researchers wishing to incorporate digital humanities tools and methods into their research, b) literary scholars wishing to engage with a broad range of users, c) scientific programmers and data scientists wishing to work with digital (both digitised and born-digital) humanities corpora and d) research coordinators wishing to provide advice and guidance throughout the research project lifecycle where digital tools, methods or collections are used.

CLS INFRA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement: 101004984

Figure 1- Ghent University – One-Page Overview

2.3 Application procedure

How to apply

For each call, applications had to be submitted through a dedicated website that was created at the beginning of the project with the purpose of managing the whole process. The website was hosted on Sciencesconf³, a multilingual and configurable platform designed to support the management of various stages in organising a conference or a call for proposals. The website is accessible at the following address: <https://clsinfratna.sciencescall.org>⁴.

Participants were asked to:

- Complete an application form, which included information about the selected host institution(s), the number of weeks requested, the preferred start date of the fellowship, and some personal details such as recent publications, current professional position, institution of affiliation, and a short project abstract;
- A curriculum vitae of maximum 2 pages;
- A detailed description of the research project related to Computational Literary Studies, including an explanation of why a visit to the chosen infrastructure was particularly relevant to the project (maximum 1,200 words);
- A recommendation letter (optional).

As previously mentioned, it was strongly recommended to contact the host institutions before submitting the application.

Applicants had to satisfy the following conditions in order to be eligible for a CLS fellowship grant:

- a) Applicants were required to work in an EU Member State or in a Horizon 2020 Associated Country⁵. Following the European Commission's decision to suspend cooperation with Russian entities in research, science, and innovation⁶, applicants working in Russian organisations were not eligible until further notice.

³ <https://www.sciencesconf.org/en/>, last accessed on 27 August 2025).

⁴ Last accessed on 19 August 2025.

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/3cpart/h2020-hi-list-ac_en.pdf (last accessed on 19 August 2025).

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_22_1544 (last accessed on 19 August 2025).

b) Applicants had to work or study in a country other than the one where the host institution was located (e.g., a researcher working in Spain could not select Madrid as a potential destination).

c) The subject of the research proposal had to be related to the field of literary studies and/or computational literary studies.

d) Only applicants who were permitted to disseminate the results generated under the action could benefit from the access, unless the users were working for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)⁷.

e) Although priority was given to new applicants, researchers who had previously received a fellowship grant were allowed to submit a new application if their research project could benefit from another visit. However, the total time spent in one or more research institutions was not to exceed three months during the course of the project. Furthermore, a second application could only be submitted after the previous visit had effectively taken place.

f) Teams of researchers (users) led by a ‘user group leader’ (as identified in Article 16 of the Horizon 2020 Annotated Grant Agreement⁸) were also eligible to apply. Due to potential difficulties in hosting and supporting more than one researcher per call, it was recommended to contact the hosting institution prior to submission.

Furthermore, access for user groups with a majority of users not working in an EU or associated country was limited to 20% of the total number of units of access provided under the grant. As the 20% ceiling had been reached during the fifth call, applications from scholars based outside the EU or Horizon 2020 Associated Countries were deemed ineligible in the sixth and last call.

A scholar based at a Russian university submitted a successful application during the first call at the end of 2021. The European Commission’s decision to suspend cooperation with Russian entities in research, science, and innovation was issued during the scholar’s visit. This decision affected the financing of Transnational Access (TNA) for Russian researchers under the Research Infrastructures programmes, as researchers affiliated with Russian public entities were excluded from access.

Despite this, it was decided that the already ongoing TNA fellowship would be completed as initially agreed, and not terminated, as doing so would have caused personal and financial harm

⁷ Definition of SMEs according to the European Union https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/sme-definition_en (last accessed on 19 August 2025).

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf, p. 163 (last accessed on 19 August 2025).

to the fellow. From the second call onward, applicants working in Russian organisations were deemed ineligible until further notice.

Evaluation

Applications were reviewed by a selection panel composed of renowned experts in Computational Literary Studies. The selection panel assessed all proposals received and recommended a shortlist of applicants to benefit from the fellowship. The panel based its decisions on the scientific merit of the applications, as well as the potential impact on the applicant's research environment.

The selection panel were composed of selected members of the project External Advisory Board (EAB) and project members. According to Article 16.1 of the Grant Agreement, the selection panel was required to be composed of international experts in the field, with at least half being independent from the beneficiaries. However, in some calls, this proportion was not fully met. Limited availability of members from the External Advisory Board had to be compensated for by including experts affiliated with the beneficiaries. When possible, these internal panel members were not involved in the TNA work package. Furthermore, the CLS INFRA consortium took all necessary measures to prevent potential conflicts of interest.

The EAB was composed as follows⁹:

- **Ioana Galleron**, Professor of French Literature and Digital Humanities at the New Sorbonne University;
- **Evelyn Gius**, Professor for Digital Philology at TU Darmstadt;
- **Laura McGrath**, Assistant Professor at Temple University;
- **John Nerbonne**, Honorary professor at the Philologische Fakultät, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg;
- **Petr Plecháč**, researcher at the Institute of Czech Literature;
- **Sandra Richter**, head of the Modern German Literature Department at the University of Stuttgart;
- **Maxim Romanov**, Junior Research Group Leader at the University of Hamburg;
- **Ted Underwood**, Professor of English and Information Sciences at the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign.

The selection panel based its decisions on the following criteria, all of which were equally weighted in the evaluation process:

- Quality of the fit between the proposal and the proposed host institution;

⁹ The stated institutional affiliations and positions reflect the situation at the time of the EAB members' selection and may no longer be current.

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- Quality of the research or teaching idea;
- Quality of the implementation plan;
- Potential impact on the applicant's research, home institution, or wider community.

Furthermore, the selection panel paid particular attention to the applicants' motivation and their prior efforts to gain proficiency in the field. In cases where applicants received the same weighted score, preference was given to scholars from regions and communities with fewer training and educational opportunities.

Notification

The outcomes of the review were communicated within 6 to 8 weeks of submission. A standard set of notification emails was prepared by Work Package 2 to communicate the results. In cases of successful evaluation, applicants were asked to confirm within two weeks whether they intended to take up the fellowship.

In some circumstances, a reserve list was created with candidates whose applications met the standards required for funding but ranked lower. Notification emails were sent accordingly. In all cases, feedback was provided upon request.

3. Communication and Dissemination activities

Great attention was dedicated to advertising the calls as widely as possible. The work was carried out by Work Package 9 in collaboration with Work Package 2, aiming to identify appropriate communication measures and tools, define and engage the target audience, and promote the TNA opportunities within the CLS INFRA project. Initially, all relevant networks, mailing lists, and institutional contacts related to literary studies were identified. Information about the open calls was communicated primarily through the project's official communication channels - namely, the CLS INFRA Twitter/X page, Bluesky (towards the end of the project), and the project website - and was also disseminated directly via the aforementioned mailing lists and topic-relevant groups. Additionally, the communication channels of CLS INFRA partner institutions were used to further spread information about the TNA calls.

An internal document was released outlining key elements for an impactful dissemination strategy. This document identified the target audience for outreach, proposed dissemination channels (such as mailing lists, social media, and online platforms), and suggested appropriate promotional materials. It also highlighted specific dissemination activities designed to strengthen outreach efforts. Finally, the strategic document included a checklist to be implemented at different stages of the TNA process: prior to the announcement of the call, during the evaluation phase, and throughout and after the fellowships.

To increase the impact of the CLS INFRA Fellowship Programme and to encourage potential applicants to prepare and submit their project proposals, a series of parallel initiatives were carried out.

3.1 TNA Archive

Participants were asked to fill in a template to reflect on their fellowship experience. It included a short introduction with their research questions, a description of their methodology, an overview of the research visit and its outcomes, and some thoughts on possible future work.

These activity reports were collected and published on the CLS INFRA website in a dedicated section called the **TNA Archive**¹⁰. The archive also features interviews and/or presentations from the 51 TNA Fellows, offering additional insights into their projects and experiences.

The content will be preserved for long-term archiving after the end of the project.

¹⁰ <https://clsinfra.io/opportunities/tnafellowships/tna-archive/> (last accessed on 19 August 2025).

3.2 YouTube

The CLS INFRA YouTube channel¹¹, launched on 23 September 2021, is also a valuable resource featuring interviews and project presentations. As of today, video content from at least 25 TNA Fellows is available on the channel.

3.3 Social media

Information about the upcoming calls, as well as promotional material, interviews, presentations, outcomes, and call results, was actively shared through social media. Initially, the main platform used was Twitter (renamed X in 2023). Toward the end of the project, BlueSky was adopted as an alternative due to concerns over the policies implemented by X.

Figure 2 - Example of a post about the TNA shared on BlueSky

3.4 TNA communication statistics

In the application form, applicants were asked to indicate how they heard about the CLS INFRA TNA Fellowship grants. The following options were included in the list:

- CLS INFRA communication channel(s);
- Project partner communication channel(s);
- Other institutional communication channel(s);
- Personal contact;
- Event (conference, workshop etc.);
- Press;
- Other.

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/@clsinfra6863> (last accessed on 19 August 2025).

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Applicants were allowed to select more than one option. The most frequently selected source was “CLS INFRA communication channel(s),” chosen by 38.73% of respondents. This indicates that the communication and dissemination efforts carried out by Work Package 2 were highly effective in raising awareness about the calls.

Networking was also an important way applicants heard about the opportunity, with 19.72% selecting “personal contact.” “Other institutional communication channels” were chosen by 14.79% of respondents, likely referring to community mailing lists or similar networks.

The option “other” was selected by 9.75% of respondents, though it does not provide clear insight into where the information was discovered. Both “event (conference, workshop, etc.)” and “project partner communication channels” were selected by 8.45% of respondents. Only one applicant indicated “press” as their source.

It is interesting to note that the option “event (conference, workshop, etc.)” was not selected at all during the first three calls but saw multiple selections starting from the fourth call. This trend likely reflects the increased promotion of the opportunity during Training Schools and other CLS INFRA-related events.

Unfortunately, due to a technical issue, it was not possible to collect statistics on page views from the dedicated CLS INFRA TNA Fellowship website.

More information on the communication and dissemination activities can be found in Deliverable 2.2 *Final Report on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation*, which also includes refined statistics related to the Transnational Access activity.

4. Calls and fellowships granted

4.1 TNA Calls: Overall Results

A total of six calls were launched throughout the project, despite only three being originally planned in the Grant Agreement. This decision was unanimously taken by the Consortium for two main reasons: first, to consolidate communication and dissemination efforts and build on the improved recognition of the CLS INFRA project; and second, to adjust the call requirements where needed and allow for a more flexible redistribution of weeks among partners, if necessary.

This approach proved to be effective, as the number of submitted applications rose steadily up to the fifth call, then declined for the final call, partly due to the limited number of available places. Overall, a total of 108 applications were received (2 of which were ineligible), and 51 projects were selected for funding. It is worth noting that one applicant was funded twice (in the 4th and 6th calls), while one successful application in the 6th call was submitted by a team of two researchers. Furthermore, two applications were positively evaluated and selected for funding, although the fellowships ultimately did not take place due to personal reasons or lack of communication.

More detailed statistics regarding gender balance, geographical balance and career level will be presented in the next section. Below, the researchers selected for funding are listed, including their institution of affiliation, their host institution, the name of their project, the period of stay and the number of access units provided (weeks). The abstracts for each project can be found in Annex I of this document.

4.2 1st call (1 November 2021 - 6 December 2021)

The first CLS INFRA TNA call was launched on 1 November 2021, with a deadline set for 6 December 2021. A total of 15 applications were received, of which 11 were selected for funding. However, one successful applicant did not respond to the notification email, and as a result, the fellowship did not take place. The 10 successful projects from the first call were as follows:

Name	Institution of affiliation	Host institution ¹²	Project	Period of stay	Number of weeks
Ivan Pozdniakov	Higher School of Economics* ¹³	University of Potsdam	Building an R Package and Web Application to Interact Within a Digital Ecosystem for Literary Studies	15 April - 16 June 2022	8

¹² In a few cases, the institution of affiliation had changed by the time the application was submitted and the fellowship took place. In this section, we indicate the institution of affiliation as provided in the application form.

¹³ It indicates that the institution of affiliation is located outside the EU and the Horizon 2020 Associated Countries.

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Srishti Sharma	N.A.*	Ghent University	Can a book make you happy? Predicting emotional links between genre, plot, and reader response	23 April - 17 July 2022	12
Petr Porizka	Palacky University in Olomouc	University of Potsdam	CapekDraCor & CzeDraCor: Capek Drama Corpus & Czech Drama Corpus	19 September - 16 December 2022	8
Andressa Rodrigues Gomide	Universidade de Coimbra	Trier University	Compiling a literary corpus with minimal resources	26 September - 02 December 2022	10
Svetlana Yatsyk	École normale supérieure	UNED	From a manual for slow reading to the reference text: a diachronic analysis of circulation of "Breviloquium de virtutibus"	6 May - 2 June 2022	4
Riva Quiroga	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile* / ProgHist Ltd.	Charles University	Improving Part of Speech Tagging for Latin-American Spanish Corpora	13 April - 8 July 2022	12
Nikolche Mickoski	Macedonian Academy of Sciences and Arts	UNED	Macedonian Poetry Corpus	10 May - 16 June 2022	6
Dario del Fante	University of Padova	UNED	Metaphors of Crisis - Metaphorical Patterns Across Discourses in Literature and Newspapers	2 September - 7 October 2022	5
Constanta Burlacu	University of Oxford	Charles University	Psalms 77 - Text Annotation and Linguistic Corpus Compilation for 16th Century Old Romanian	18 September - 11 December 2022	12
Louis Burnard	Lou Burnard Consulting	University of Galway	Reviving the Victorian Plays Project	First visit: 21 March - 9 April 2022; second visit: 20 - 27 July 2022	4

4.3 2nd call (18 April 2022 - 23 May 2022)

The second CLS INFRA TNA call was launched on 18 April 2022, with a deadline set for 23 May 2022. A total of 9 applications were received, one of which was ineligible. Four projects were selected for funding, as follows:

Name	Institution of affiliation	Host institution	Project	Period of stay	Number of weeks
Cassandra Ulph	University of Manchester	University of Galway	Developing attribute-based sentiment analysis model for Romantic-period letters	6 February - 21 March 2023	8
Laura Soffiantini	Scuola Normale Superiore	Ghent University	Formulaic language in Latin funerary epigraphy	21 August - 31 October 2022	10
Nisa Kirbaç	KU Leuven	Charles University	Dead but Turkish: An NLP Analysis of the Obituaries of the Turkish Community in Belgium	12 June - 7 July 2023	4
Theodorus Fransen	NUI Galway	Charles University	From Modern to Early Irish: retrogressive diachronic morphological tagging methods and UD tagset interoperability solutions based on detailed linguistic analysis	21 September - 21 December 2022	12

4.4 3rd call (7 November 2022 - 5 December 2022)

The third CLS INFRA TNA call was launched on 7 November 2022, with a deadline set for 5 December 2022. A total of 12 applications were received and 7 projects were selected for funding, as follows:

Name	Institution of affiliation	Host institution	Project	Period of stay	Number of weeks
Federico Pianzola	University of Groningen	University of Potsdam	Programmable corpora as linked data	27 March - 21 April 2023	4

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Khanim Garayeva	University of Szeged	UNED	Calculation of similarities or distances in Peter Ackroyd's historiographic metafiction and lexical diversity in Dan Brown's straightforward storytelling	28 April - 28 May 2023	4
Lara Nuges	University of Basel	Trier University	Building a digital corpus of vaudeville to study humour: issues and challenges	27 February - 6 April 2023	6
Richard Zmelik	Palacký University in Olomouc	Trier University	Building a literary corpus of 19th century Czech prose	1 October - 27 October 2023	4
Roxana Patras	"Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi	Trier University	Criss-crossing Novel Illustrations and DALL-E-generated Images: toward a data-rich ekphrasis	14 June - 19 July 2023	5
Jana-Katharina Mende	Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg	Austrian Academy of Sciences	Monolingualism Deconstructed: Modelling Hidden and Invisible Multilingualism in German literature (1790-1890)	First visit: 4 March - 29 March 2024; second visit: 10 June - 14 June 2024	5
Maciej Maryl	Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences	University of Galway	Social Network Analysis of Career Trajectories in Polish Literature After 1989	First visit: 10 June - 7 July; second visit: 2 December - 16 December	4

4.5 4th call (2 May 2023 - 30 May 2023)

The fourth CLS INFRA TNA call was launched on 2 May 2023, with a deadline set for 30 May 2022. A total of 21 applications were received and 12 projects were selected for funding, as follows:

Name	Institution of affiliation	Host institution	Project	Period of stay	Number of weeks
Ewa Data-Bukowska	Jagiellonian University	Charles University	The principle of sustainability as the basis for the translator's stylistic creation	1 February - 29 February 2024	4

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

Wiktor Dziemski	Jagiellonian University	UNED	Can't you see what I'm going through? Stylometrical analysis of Marcus Tullius Cicero's works in their correlation to the author's life	26 November - 8 December 2023	2
Eduardo Fernández Guerrero	European University Institute	UNED	Distant reading of early modern prophecies across Europe: corpus formation and testing	4 October - 20 December 2023	12
Rocio Hernández-Arias	University of Vigo	Austrian Academy of Sciences	Digital Academic Edition of 'O anarquista' (1924), by Leandro Pita	10 June - 30 August 2024	12
Elisabeth Joyce	Pennsylvania Western University	UNED	The New York School of Poetry: A distant reading of affinities	3 May - 7 June	4
Jyothi Justin	Indian Institute of Technology Indore (IITI)*	UNED	Seeing the Unseen: Locating the Women of Independent India's Unheard Dalit Massacres	6 March - 8 May 2024	9
Natalia Kamovnikova	independent researcher	Austrian Academy of Sciences	Corpus-building, classification, and preservation of contemporary anti-war poetry in the context of its electronic and social vulnerability	25 March - 16 June 2024	12
Marko Milosev	Central European University	UNED	Words to actions: How and if ideology translates to violence in the case of interwar fascist organizations	8 January - 8 February 2024	4
Julia Neugarten	Radboud University	Ghent University	Catching Feelings: Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Fanfiction about Greek Myth	13 May - 30 June 2024	6
Emrah Peksoy	Kahramanmaraş İstiklal University	Austrian Academy of Sciences	Dictionary Building for Narrative Arc	2 June - 4 July 2024	9

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

Levente Seláf	Eötvös Loránd University	Charles University	Comparative Analysis of Poetical Texts with Digital Tools	4 March - 26 April 2024	8
Haimo Stiemer	Technical University Darmstadt	University of Galway	The clash of the modernists - Comparing the expressionist journal "Der Sturm" and the journal "Der Querschnitt" from the Weimar Republic	24 February - 5 April 2024	6

4.6 5th call (6 November 2023 - 4 December 2023)

The fifth CLS INFRA TNA call was launched on 6 November 2023, with a deadline set for 4 December 2023. A total of 38 applications (one of which was ineligible) were received and 12 projects were selected for funding, as follows:

Name	Institution of affiliation	Host institution	Project	Period of stay	Number of weeks
Lisa Teichmann	Université de Montréal*	Austrian Academy of Sciences	Translational Trajectories of German Fiction in the German and Austrian National Libraries	First visit: 25 March - 3 May 2024; second visit: 21 May - 14 June 2024	10
Simone Marcenaro	Università del Molise	University of Galway	Harmonizing Artistry: exploring the collaboration between AI and human expertise in translating Galician-Portuguese Troubadour poetry (phase one)	17 June – 5 July 2024	3
Patricia Garcia	UNED	University of Galway	Graphs of the Social Networks of Spanish Women Writers of Irish Descent in the 18th Century	9 May – 5 June	4
Floriana Ceresato	Università degli Studi di Padova	University of Galway	The digital franco-italian "Anseis de Carthage"	13 May – 7 July	8

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

Vladimir Polomac	University of Kragujevac	Charles University	Universal Dependencies for Old Serbian and Serbian Church Slavonic: Creating a training data set for lemmatization and morphosyntactic annotation using UDPipe	1 June – 30 June 2024	4
Anna Baryshnikova	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nuremberg	Charles University	Digital Analysis of the Baltic Germans' Monthly Newspaper "Baltische Briefe": Employing Named-Entity Recognition Methods and Historical GIS to Construct a Digital Map of the Most Significant Places in the Baltic Germans' Homeland	1 September 2024 - 26 October 2024	8
Szemes Botond	HUN-REN Research Centre for the Humanities, Institute for Literary Studies	University of Potsdam	New Metrics for Computational Drama Analysis	1 April - 30 April 2024	4
Lucas van der Deijl	University of Groningen	University of Potsdam	Deploying DutchDraCor. Integrating 150 early modern Dutch plays (1550-1700) into the infrastructure of the Drama Corpora Project (DraCor)	01 April - 26 April 2024	4
Agnieszka Szulińska	Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences	University of Potsdam	Behind the scenes. Integrating TEI Panorama of Polish drama data into DraCor Programmable Corpora	11 March - 9 April 2024	4
Radim Hladík	Czech Academy of Sciences	Trier University	A sprint for FAIRer data: Development of features for data exchange and publication in research software for qualitative data analysis	14 April - 18 May 2024	5

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

Kim Byungjun	Center for Digital Humanities & Computational Social Sciences, KAIST*	Trier University	Integrative Approaches in Computational Literary Studies and Global Knowledge Structures	25 March - 21 May 2024	8
Rozalia Słodczyk	Institute of Polish Language (Polish Academy of Sciences), Kraków	Trier University	Operationalising the nocturne genre - comparative traditional and digital humanities research using i.a. topic modeling on the example of contemporary Polish and Italian poetry	03 June - 07 June 2024	1 ¹⁴

4.7 6th call (June 2025 - November 2025, rolling call)

The sixth CLS INFRA TNA call was organised on a rolling basis with the following deadlines: 29 July 2024; 9 September 2024; 21 October 2024; 25 November 2024.

A total of 13 applications were received during this period, one of which was submitted by a team of two researchers. Six projects were selected for funding, as follows:

Name	Institution of affiliation	Host institution	Project	Period of stay	Number of weeks
Alyaxey Yaskevich	University of Warsaw	Charles University	Exploring classical Belarusian fiction with the methods of corpus and computational linguistics	3 November 2024 - 25 January 2025	12
Anna Medrzecka	Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences	Charles University	Polish poetry corpus: creation, integration with PoeTree, computational poetics	15 December 2024 - 27 February 2025	6
Mercedes de Luis Andrés	University of Klagenfurt - Austrian Academy of Sciences	University of Galway	Book Clubs in Journalism Culture - BoJo Club	05 January - 28 February 2025	7

¹⁴ Due to personal reasons, the fellowship could not be resumed as initially planned.

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

Kathryn Laing / Geraldine Brassil	Mary Immaculate College, University of Limerick	Trier University	Enhancing the Irish Women's Writing Network 1880-1920 Website: Data Capture, Digitisation, Visualisation	13 January - 24 January 2025	4 (2 weeks per fellow)
Maria-Corina Dimitriu	"Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi	Trier University	Parametrization Guidelines in StyloR for the Romanian Language	22 October - 6 November 2024	2
Ewa Data-Bukowska	Jagiellonian University	Charles University	What characterizes the Polish novel Trans-Atlantyk by W. Gombrowicz is unconventional syntax. Does the Swedish translation of the novel preserve the syntactic unconventionality? How can we measure that?	3 February - 27 February 2025	4

5. Key statistics

In this section, statistics regarding units of access provided, success rates, gender balance, geographical coverage and career level are presented. Overall, the project achieved a good balance in terms of gender and geographical inclusivity, while stronger measures should have been taken to better include undergraduates and postgraduates, whose success rates were significantly lower compared to other categories.

5.1 Units of access

As mentioned in the previous section, 51 fellowships were awarded over the course of the project, amounting to a total of 333 weeks of access. While this is slightly below the number of weeks originally planned in the Grant Agreement, nearly 90% of the intended access was ultimately delivered.

There were some imbalances among the participating institutions: while some were able to host a higher number of visits than initially planned, others had to slightly reduce their initial expectations due to various administrative or organisational constraints.

After the allocation of fellowships in the sixth and final call, the final institutional breakdown is presented below:

Name of the institution	Actual units of access	Planned units of access	Actual number of projects	Estimated number of projects	% of access delivered
Ghent University	28	36	3	3	77,78%
University of Galway	44	48	8	6	91,67%
Austrian Academy of Sciences	48	72	5	6	66,67%
Charles University	86	72	11	6	119,44%
University of Potsdam	32	24	6	3	133,33%
Trier University	45	48	9	6	93,75%
UNED	50	72	9	6	69,44%
Total	333	372	51	36	89,52%

It is worth noting that longer visits, ranging from 8 to 12 weeks, were originally planned. However, such extended stays often proved more difficult to arrange and implement. The average duration per participant was **6.5 weeks**, which may indicate a more realistic and effective timeframe for achieving meaningful scientific outcomes and receive hands-on training, while accommodating professional and personal constraints.

When analysing the percentage of access delivered compared to the original planning, it can be noted that a higher number of fellowships were awarded over the course of the project. This is undoubtedly a positive outcome, as it allowed a greater number of scholars to benefit from the Transnational Access scheme, even if for a shorter period of time on average.

Certain institutions, such as the University of Potsdam and Charles University, were able to provide a higher number of access units by allocating additional resources to fund successful applicants.

The University of Galway and Trier University delivered a slightly lower number of access units than originally planned, although both still achieved over 90% of their targets. In the case of Trier University, this was due to a fellowship that could not be resumed because of personal constraints.

Ghent University, UNED, and the Austrian Academy of Sciences were unable to deliver more than 80% of their initial targets. This was due to a range of factors. At Ghent University, one fellowship awarded to a researcher based in India proved significantly more expensive than average, impacting the total number of units delivered. UNED faced extended building closures due to renovations, which disrupted access for a considerable period. In the case of the Austrian Academy of Sciences, this gap was primarily due to a lack of applications received during the early calls.

5.2 Gender Balance

Particular attention was given by the Consortium to ensuring that the participation rates of both women and men were as close as possible to 50%. The overall results were satisfactory in this respect: of a total of 108 applications, 61¹⁵ (56.48%) were submitted by women scholars, while 47 (43.52%) were submitted by men. The proportion is very similar when considering the success rate: 29 applications (56.86%) submitted by women scholars were accepted, compared to 22 applications (43.14%) submitted by men scholars. A graphical representation is given below:

¹⁵ For the sake of simplicity, a team application composed of two women scholars is considered here as one.

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

Figure 3 - Gender balance

5.3 Geographical coverage

First of all, we indicate here the country of the applicant's institution of affiliation, not their nationality, which adds even greater diversity to the scheme. Overall, applications were received from 32 different countries, 8 of which were from outside the European Union (or Horizon Europe–associated countries), totaling 25 applications (23% of the total). This interest from beyond Europe demonstrates that the Transnational Access scheme is regarded as a valuable instrument worldwide, despite potential administrative burdens.

While most applications were received from Poland (12), it is noteworthy that India ranked second - alongside Italy - with a total of 10 applications, highlighting strong interest. A relatively high number of applications were also received from Spain (8), Germany (6), and the United States (6).

The image below shows the number of applications received from each country and also highlights the number of successful applications.

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

Figure 4 - Number of applications received from each country. In green, the total number of applications, in violet, the number of successful projects.

Figure 5 - Distribution of submitted applications by country.

It is worth noting that, while good geographical coverage was achieved, some areas or countries were underrepresented or missing—such as Scandinavia, the Baltic countries, and, with a few exceptions, Southeastern Europe. It is unclear whether this was due to a lack of more targeted communication or to potential bottlenecks within the CLS community based in those regions. Nevertheless, the overall reach was quite positive, thanks in part to the continuous communication and dissemination efforts coordinated by Work Package 2. The image below illustrates the distribution of submitted applications by country.

The submitted applications per country, including the number of successful ones and the success rate (expressed as a percentage), are listed below:

Country	Applications	of which successful	Success rate
Albania	1	0	0%
Austria	2	2	100%
Belarus	1	0	0%
Belgium	2	1	50%
Canada	2	1	50%
Chile	1	1	100%
China	1	0	0%
Cyprus	1	0	0%
Czech Republic	5	3	60%
France	5	2	40%
Germany	6	3	50%
Hungary	5	3	60%
India	10	2	20%
Ireland	4	2	50%
Israel	1	0	0%
Italy	10	5	50%

Country	Applications	of which successful	Success rate
Netherlands	4	3	75%
Nigeria	2	0	0%
North Macedonia	1	1	100%
Poland	12	8	66,67%
Portugal	1	1	100%
Romania	3	2	66,67%
Russia	1	1	100%
Serbia	3	1	33,33%
Slovakia	1	1	100%
Slovenia	2	0	0%
South Korea	1	1	100%
Spain	8	2	25%
Switzerland	1	1	100%
Turkey	3	1	33,33%
United Kingdom	2	2	100%
USA	6	1	16,67%

5.4 Success rates

A total of 108 applications were received during the course of the project, of which 2 were ineligible. Of the eligible applications, 51 were selected for funding, resulting in a success rate of 47.22%.

The success rates for each call are summarized below:

	Applications	Ineligible	of which successful	Success rate
1st call	15	0	10	66.67%
2nd call	9	1	4	44.44%
3rd call	12	0	7	58.33%

4th call	21	0	12	57.14%
5th call	38	1	12	31.58%
6th call	13	0	6	46.15%
Total	108	2	51	47.22%

It is worth noting that the number of applications increased significantly after the midpoint of the project, culminating in an exceptional 38 applications received for the fifth call. This suggests that the communication and dissemination efforts were effective, and that the opportunity was perceived as valuable by the research community. The relative decline in applications for the sixth and final call was likely a result of the scarcity of remaining slots.

In 9 cases, unsuccessful projects were resubmitted in subsequent calls, and 5 of them (55.56%) were awarded funding.

	2nd call	3rd call	4th call	5th call	6th call	Total
Nb. resubmissions	0	3	0	4	2	9
of which successful	0	3	0	1	1	5

5.5 Career levels

In the application form, applicants were asked to indicate their career level at the time of submission. The options available for selection were:

- Undergraduate;
- Postgraduate;
- Post-doc researcher;
- Technician;
- Experienced researcher;
- Other (with a free-text field provided).

There were some known limitations to the approach, notably the reliance on applicants' self-evaluation, the lack of detailed explanations for each field in the form, and the allowance of multiple-choice answers.

Nevertheless, the statistics are quite interesting and could provide valuable insights for shaping similar initiatives in the future. The table hereafter shows the number of successful applications in relation to the career level¹⁶

¹⁶ It should be noted that two additional rows, "no position" and "not indicated", have been added to the table compared to the initial list. These categories have been counted separately.

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Career level	Applications	of which successful	Success rate
Undergraduate	1	0	0%
Postgraduate	44	16	36,36%
Post-doc researcher	23	14	60,87%
Technician	0	0	0%
Experienced researcher	33	18	54,55%
Other	5	2	40%
No position	1	1	100%
Not indicated	1	0	0%

We can highlight the high proportion of applications received from postgraduates (41% of the total), although a relatively low number of these were ultimately retained for funding compared to other career levels. On the other hand, post-doc researchers and experienced researchers achieved significantly higher success rates. This is likely due to their greater experience in writing concise proposals, as well as their ability to refine the content after feedback from the targeted host institutions. Nevertheless, the number of postgraduates who were awarded fellowships was satisfactory. Specific training to improve proposal-writing skills, or a more targeted approach to support postgraduates in TNA schemes within the Humanities, could be developed for future Transnational Access initiatives.

6. Impact

6.1 Survey

To better understand the impact of the TNA scheme, a survey was sent in February 2025 to, among others, all TNA participants. The survey had two main objectives: first, to identify training needs and preferred learning formats in order to organise online workshops on various CLS-related topics; second, to gather qualitative data about participants' experiences with the TNA scheme or the Training Schools, including which aspects, if any, were considered important.

Of the 46 complete responses received, 22 came from TNA fellows. The following questions, related to their experience as TNA grant holders, were asked:

- *Do you think that participating in a CLS INFRA Training School and/or in the TNA programme had a positive impact on your professional career?*
 - 7- Strongly agree
 - [...]
 - 1. Strongly disagree

- *If you think that participating in a CLS INFRA Training School and/or in the TNA programme had a positive impact on your professional career, could you please let us know where you benefited the most (multiple choice question)?*
 - Acquisition of new professional competencies
 - Discovery of new tools/methods/standards
 - Crucial advancements in the current research project
 - Unforeseen research questions that emerged after participating to CLS INFRA opportunities
 - Opportunities for developing a new research project
 - Academic publication(s) made possible
 - Improvement in career stage (promotion, new employment opportunities)
 - Networking
 - Participation to similar initiatives
 - I don't think it had an impact

- *Please describe more in details how participating to a training opportunity within CLS INFRA had an impact to your professional career (free text).*

- *What are your suggestions to improve the overall experience? (free text).*

Regarding the first question, “*Do you think that participating in a CLS INFRA Training School and/or in the TNA programme had a positive impact on your professional career?*”, the average

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

response. based on a Likert scale, was **6.23 out of 7¹⁷**, indicating a strong agreement on the positive impact of the experience. In only one case was dissatisfaction clearly expressed, likely due to differing expectations regarding the support that should have been provided.

When asked, *“If you think that participating in a CLS INFRA Training School and/or in the TNA programme had a positive impact on your professional career, could you please let us know where you benefited?”* the answers, not surprisingly, highlighted that the TNA was important for **discovering new tools, methods, and standards** (16 occurrences), **networking** (14 occurrences), and **acquiring new professional competencies** (13 occurrences). Eleven respondents indicated that the TNA was beneficial for achieving **crucial advancements in their current research projects**, and eight answered that the TNA provided opportunities for **developing new research projects**. With six occurrences each, respondents also noted that **unforeseen research questions emerged** after participating in CLS INFRA opportunities, and that **academic publication(s) were made possible**.

In two cases, the TNA was **beneficial for career advancement** (promotion or new employment opportunities) and important for **participating in similar initiatives**. Finally, in one case, the respondent indicated that there was **no evident impact**.

Figure 6 - Question: *If you think that participating in a CLS INFRA Training School and/or in the TNA programme had a positive impact on your professional career, could you please let us know where you benefited?*

¹⁷ Only responses from TNA fellows are considered in this analysis.

Participants were also invited to freely describe how taking part in a training opportunity within CLS INFRA impacted their professional careers. As the question was optional, not everyone responded. Nevertheless, some interesting feedback was received.

The following quotes highlight some of the feedback on the impact:

- *“I learned a lot about tools that I can use in analyzing text.”*
- *“I had the opportunity of expanding my research network and I gained new knowledge for future projects.”*
- *“I experienced firsthand the infrastructure underlying digital literary studies in Europe. This experience was a significant boost in my journey to becoming an assistant professor. In particular, I realized that Linked Open Data plays a crucial role in literary research, and it provided me with the opportunity to integrate it into my own work.”*
- *“During my CLSInfra fellowship I learned new methods to structure the core of my research project, I learned to think differently about literary studies in general, getting to know more data based approaches and goes to connect those to traditional literary studies. I met people who work in a similar style, combining archive work and digital tools. All that led to several new cooperations, funding opportunities and research ideas. And it was fun! It also influenced my teaching and I use several of the skills I gained during the training school and fellowship for my own seminars.”*
- *“As a junior research associate, I am glad for the opportunity of having been a CLS INFRA Fellow. During my fellowship, I learned a lot of new skills and methods directly linked to my research activity, which I could share with my research colleagues. Moreover, I am still in touch with my mentor, who has continued to give me feedback and advice related to my research projects in Digital Humanities. This is very valuable to me, since Digital Humanities is an emerging field in my country, with very few specialists and no available educational programs. Last but not least, the research done during my fellowship laid the groundwork for my first important research project, which I hope will soon materialise into my first international conference presentation and my first paper in an international publication.”*
- *“Thanks to the scholarship, I learned modern language processing. I hope that manual data counting is a thing of the past. I have made a very valuable scientific contact and I hope it will be developed. The quality of my publications will improve.”*
- *“The new project developed make me write an academic monography.”*
- *“It improved my research knowledge and skills, my professional network and my CV.”*

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- *“The most important benefit of taking part in the CLS Infra Fellowship was networking - I got in touch with a group of CLS professionals, learned about their work and methods. I was able to observe the creation of the data collection tools, and I learned about the process of entering data into the corpus.”*
- *“The opportunity was a recent one so the impact is not immediately obvious, but more expertise in the field of Computational Literary Studies can only enhance one’s research, publications and career options.”*
- *“Unfortunately, my CLS INFRA Fellowship did not have much of an impact on my career because I did most of the work alone, without adequate support. I would have liked a mentor, experienced in digital humanities, who would follow me step by step so that I could acquire the necessary knowledge for the proper development of my project.”*

These quotes support the aspects of the TNA scheme that were identified as valuable in the previous question: networking opportunities, the chance to learn new tools or methods, the acquisition of new skills and the support received to make significant advancements in research projects. Only one review was negative, likely due to unfortunate circumstances at the host institution during the time of the fellowship. Overall, the same institution received positive feedback.

The last question was the following: *“What are your suggestions to improve the overall experience?”*. The answer was optional.

Few suggestions were received, as most respondents expressed satisfaction with the overall experience. One participant suggested the creation of a more stable, long-term research network to facilitate continued collaboration. In another case, the respondent felt that the fellowship duration was too short and proposed longer visits, though this would exceed the scope of the TNA scheme. One review noted some difficulty in finding accommodation due to the limited time available before the start of the fellowship, and suggested that host institutions consider offering on-campus housing. However, in most cases, participants reported having sufficient time and receiving adequate support in securing suitable accommodation.

Annex II of this document provides a list of publications and research outputs available for consultation.

6.2 Closing event

On 2 July 2025, CLS INFRA hosted a workshop in Kraków to celebrate the closing of the project. The event took place ahead of the 4th Annual Conference of Computational Literary Studies. It covered the outcomes of the project, briefly presenting its most important findings, as well as a panel discussion on the future of CLS research. Furthermore, the core of the event

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focused on presentations given by selected recipients of CLS INFRA Transnational Access Fellowship Programme grants during their research stays at CLS expert institutions.

The following TNA fellows participated in the event and presented the projects conducted during their fellowships:

- Maria-Corina Dimitriu (TNA fellow at Trier University) – Parametrization Guidelines in StyloR for the Romanian Language;
- Lucas Van der Deijl (TNA fellow at University of Potsdam) – Integrating 150 early modern Dutch plays (1550-1700) into the infrastructure of the Drama Corpora Project (DraCor);
- Simone Marcenaro (TNA fellow at University of Galway) – Harmonizing Artistry: exploring the collaboration between AI and human expertise in translating Galician-Portuguese Troubadour poetry (phase one);
- Anna Mędrzecka (TNA fellow at Charles University) – Polish poetry corpus: creation, integration with PoeTree, computational poetics;
- Jana-Katharina Mende (TNA fellow at Austrian Academy of Sciences) – Monolingualism Deconstructed: Modelling Hidden and Invisible Multilingualism in German literature (1790-1890);
- Laura Soffiantini (TNA fellow at Ghent University) – Formulaic language in Latin funerary epigraphy;
- Marko Milosev (TNA fellow at UNED Madrid) – Words to Action: How and If Ideology Translates To Violence In the Case Of Interwar Fascists Organisations.

This event was not only important for showcasing their projects, but also for receiving direct feedback on their experiences and discussing the improvements that have taken place since. In most cases, the TNA fellowship represented a valuable opportunity to discover new research directions and aspects that were not initially anticipated.

Figure 7 - Group photo taken at the closing event

6.3 CLS INFRA online workshops

As part of the extension of the project until August 2025, and within the framework of Work Package 2 (in close connection with Work Package 9), it was decided to offer extended remote opportunities to former TNA fellows, including unsuccessful applicants. In this context, a “lightweight” online workshop was organised on Wednesday, 9 July 2025, hosted via Zoom, focusing on the fundamentals of network analysis for humanities scholars. The event combined historical and literary case studies with hands-on practice. Although primarily intended for both successful and unsuccessful TNA applicants, it was open to the first 150 registrants. Registration was immediately successful, with all available spots filled three weeks in advance. Anticipated no-shows were taken into account and confirmed on the day of the event. Nevertheless, around 90 participants attended the workshop, which was presented by Dr. Daniil Skorinkin, Digital Humanities Coordinator at the University of Potsdam.

Participants explored networks of literary characters, correspondence, and historical actors, and learned how to visualise and interpret these structures using accessible tools such as Gephi and EzLinavis.

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This event successfully extended the reach of the TNA programme to underrepresented groups of scholars. Furthermore, the recording will be uploaded to DARIAH-Campus¹⁸, a discovery framework and hosting platform for learning resources, allowing all interested scholars to access the workshop at any time.

Another workshop will be made available as a video recording with accompanying training materials on DARIAH-Campus later this autumn. It will be taught by Serge Heiden (partner representing École normale supérieure de Lyon, France) and will cover the application of textometry and the TXM software for textual analysis.

¹⁸ <https://campus.dariah.eu/> (last accessed on 27 August 2025).

7. Conclusion

The transnational activities undertaken by CLS INFRA have, overall, proven to be highly successful. Grant holders consistently report considerable scientific, technical, and networking value resulting from these visits. While the initial targets for access provision were ambitious, the Consortium successfully coordinated the visits and demonstrated flexibility by adjusting the programme when necessary.

The CLS INFRA Transnational Access Fellowship Programme attracted considerable interest from the beginning, which increased further as the Consortium enhanced the project's visibility and credibility through tangible outcomes. The coordination between the various Work Packages played a crucial role in facilitating smooth and efficient implementation.

While not all planned units of access could be provided, the high volume of applications and inquiries, both from the EU and internationally, has been a strong indicator of the programme's broad appeal and relevance. Furthermore, the initial objectives of achieving an acceptable gender balance and ensuring broad geographical coverage were successfully met. The TNA Fellowship Programme proved to be a valuable instrument for both early-career and more experienced researchers: the visits served as a career boost by helping early-stage researchers establish themselves in the field and guiding more experienced researchers toward new areas of study.

As evidenced by the activity reports, the host institutions provided essential scientific, technical guidance and support during the visits, helping grant holders advance their projects. Many participants indicated that the experience was valuable for discovering new tools, methods, and standards, acquiring professional competencies, and expanding their networks. Frequently, the visits played a crucial role in revealing previously unanticipated research questions, highlighting the exploratory value of the fellowships. At the same time, project members and mentors involved in the programme were inspired by new research ideas and approaches, demonstrating the vibrancy of the field and the mutual exchange of knowledge.

Overall, the CLS INFRA Transnational Access Fellowship Programme has significantly advanced knowledge and research in Computational Literature Studies by facilitating access to cutting-edge infrastructures and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. By involving a wide range of researchers across Europe and beyond, each bringing unique contributions and insights, the CLS INFRA Transnational Access Fellowship Programme undoubtedly helped achieve the overarching goals of the CLS INFRA project as a whole.

Annex I – Abstracts of Research Projects

1st call (1 November 2021 - 06 December 2021)

Ivan Pozdniakov - Building an R Package and Web Application to Interact Within a Digital Ecosystem for Literary Studies

Drama Corpora Project (DraCor) is a large and growing ecosystem for Drama analysis. DraCor is a realization of the Programmable Corpora concept and provides an access to data for plays in several drama corpora. Every drama is encoded using TEI that helps to analyze different plays and the whole corpora by access to the project's API.

The goal of the project is to develop and improve web application using Shiny (<https://shiny.dracor.org>) and R package {rdracor}(<https://github.com/dracor-org/rdracor>) for easier and more straightforward interaction with DraCor. That involves adding new features, refactoring the existing code, updating code to the current version of API, writing documentation, implementing unit-tests, writing tutorials, and updating UI (for the Shiny web application).

Srishti Sharma - Can a book make you happy? Predicting emotional links between genre, plot, and reader response

The purpose of this project is to explore the effect of emotions expressed in fictional stories on the emotions experienced by their readers. The analysis is based on a dataset of over 400 books from nine different genres and their corresponding reviews from Goodreads. Sentiment analysis is applied to calculate three types of sentiment values: the average book sentiment, the average review sentiment, and the emotional story arc of each book. Three different methods are employed: a dictionary-based approach, a transformer-based approach, and a vector-space model approach known as SentiArt. Plot types are defined by clustering the emotional story arcs using k-means with Dynamic Time Warping Barycenter Averaging (DBA) as the distance metric. Hypotheses are tested using linear regression models (ANCOVA) to analyze the covariance between the sentiment values of books and reviews.

Petr Porizka - CapekDraCor & CzeDraCor: Capek Drama Corpus

DraCor, a database of dramas created by a scientific team of the University of Potsdam contains plays in a number of languages: at present, there are 13 sub-databases in 13 languages accessible within DraCor; Czech is, however, not one of them. DraCor is a unique platform (regarding both data and tools) for analysis of literary texts that are specific with respect to both their structure (multi-layer nature) and linguistic characteristics (on the border

between written and spoken language; meta-text commentaries as well as dialogues of characters). Until present, the Czech corpus linguistics has not had any complex database of theatre plays of such a kind. The only source has been theatre plays included in the Czech National Corpus; individual plays are, however, imported in this database without any further detailed segmentation that would adequately reflect the specifics of dramas and their structure. The present project has two aims. Firstly, it aims to create a pilot database CapekDraCor that will contain all five theatre plays written by Karel Čapek, and thus establish the foundation of a database CzechDraCor that will contain theatre plays of other Czech authors. Secondly, the project aims to take benefit from a fellowship in order to gain necessary skills and knowledge for processing of the Czech version of DraCor. A fellow shall be trained in technical data processing and the subsequent interconnection to individual applications (API, SPARQL, ezlinaviz, Shiny DraCor). Project outcomes shall be used within the Czech linguistics (in university courses of Digital Humanities). Also, the newly established and unique database of Czech drama will be available to a wider professional public and may possibly serve even for secondary-school education. The project establishing the Czech version of the database will help disseminate the master international project DraCor within the Czech Academia.

Andressa Rodrigues Gomide - Compiling a literary corpus with minimal resources

This project addresses the creation of the literary subcorpus of Corpus Pluricêntrico da Língua Portuguesa (CPLP), a large reference corpus of Portuguese language varieties. Given the obstacles to deal with copyrighted documents, the aim of this project is to devise a system that allows optimal literary data collection with limited resources. To achieve that, quantitative linguistic analysis will be piloted on six literary datasets that pose distinct levels of difficulties concerning data collection. It is expected that the knowledge of how these datasets differ from each other will aid the creation of a framework that allows for fast and simple data collection that does not affect the quality of the final data.

Svetlana Yatsik - From a manual for slow reading to the reference text: a diachronic analysis of circulation of "Breviloquium de virtutibus"

John of Wales was a Franciscan theologian and preacher who taught at Oxford and later in Paris during the reign of Louis IX. This project focuses on the analysis of his first work, Breviloquium de virtutibus antiquorum principum et philosophorum, which was abundantly copied, read, and used by the network of Franciscan convents throughout Europe until the 16th century. Particular attention is given to the clarification of its literary genre, as the Breviloquium combines features of a florilegium, a preaching aid, and a mirror for princes. The study of the circulation of this treatise may contribute to a better understanding of its generic nature.

To support this analysis, a relational database is being constructed containing detailed information on the 140 known manuscripts of the Breviloquium, with a focus on their codicological features. The database includes data on scribes, bindings, ex-libris, and codicological units. In addition, each manuscript is linked to a table describing its contents, particularly the texts accompanying the Breviloquium; this allows elaborating the typology of the collections in which the work circulated.

Two digital approaches are proposed to build such a typology: factor correspondence analysis and social network analysis. The first method enables the calculation of similarity between manuscripts based on the number of shared texts. A symmetrical square matrix is created, with each row and column representing a manuscript, and each cell indicating the number of texts common to both. This matrix is then analyzed using FactoMineR to determine proximity between manuscripts. However, since the notion of proximity has only relative value, the resulting connections may remain somewhat abstract. Social network analysis is therefore used to refine and clarify the typology. This method is based on the idea that relational data can be visualized as a network: a text can be considered a link connecting two manuscripts if it is present in both, allowing building a network of manuscripts.

Riva Quiroga - Improving Part of Speech Tagging for Latin-American Spanish Corpora

Part of Speech (POS) tagging is a key step when preprocessing a corpus, as the correct assignment of parts of speech to words impacts the results of lemmatization and dependency parsing. This is particularly important in a field such as Computational Literary Studies, where identifying actions, characters, and instances of particular linguistic constructions can help researchers to gain insights about a corpus. Although POS taggers are currently available for Spanish, most of them have been trained exclusively with texts written in European Spanish, a variety that is used only by around 10% of all native speakers of this language. For example, AnCora –the biggest Spanish corpus available at <https://universaldependencies.org>, and the one used by tools such as spaCy and UDPipe– is composed only of newspaper and newswire articles written by Spanish media. As a consequence, POS taggers have lower accuracy with texts written in other varieties of Spanish, and with genres that do not rely exclusively in formal speech. This presents a serious limitation to explore corpora of Latin-American Literature using computational methods. To fill this gap, this project aims to train a model for POS tagging texts written in Latin-American Spanish. To that end, a corpus of literary and historical texts written in this variety will be used to train a model with UDPipe, a trainable pipeline for Natural Language Processing tasks developed at the Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics at Charles University, CZ. The implementation plan involves assembling the corpus, documenting the annotation process, training the new model, and evaluating its results. The outputs will include the tagged corpus (available via <https://universaldependencies.org/> for reusability), an article about the corpus and the training process, and a tutorial submitted to Programming Historian

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(<https://programminghistorian.org/>) on how to use this model to annotate and explore Latin-American literary texts.

Nikolche Mickoski - Macedonian Poetry Corpus

The project focuses on designing and creating a poetry corpus containing over 500 short poems (out of copyright) in Macedonian. The plan includes compiling a corpus based on the *Collection of the Miladinov Brothers*, which consists of approximately 660 folk songs collected from Macedonia. This collection is recognized as the first major compilation of Macedonian folk poetry. The poems are available in both modern and historical Cyrillic orthography on Wikisource (https://mk.wikisource.org/wiki/Зборник_на_Миладиновци), while the original publication is accessible through the Macedonian National Library website (<http://www.dlib.mk/bitstream/handle/68275/257/82213130.pdf>).

The goal is to make the songs available as part of an annotated corpus, using a specific tagset aligned with the LINHD – UNED model. A significant challenge in the development of the poetry corpus will be the annotation process. In addition to the absence of a national corpus for the Macedonian language, no official Part-Of-Speech (PoS) tagger currently exists for Macedonian. While several useful linguistic resources are available, the lack of a standardized PoS tagger presents an obstacle.

LINHD – UNED maintains a project dedicated to poetry and the construction of poetry corpora that are compliant with the Ontopoetry ontology. The first version of this ontology is available at <https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/results/network-of-ontologies/>. The developed Macedonian poetry corpus will include prosodic information along with other fundamental metadata. Furthermore, the corpus will be integrated into the LINHD tool Averell (<https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/results/poetrylab/averell/>).

The Macedonian poetry corpus is intended to serve as a long-term resource and will provide a solid infrastructure for the continued expansion and integration of additional poems.

Dario del Fante - Metaphors of Crisis – Metaphorical Patterns Across Discourses in Literature and Newspapers

The international outbreak of Coronavirus has radically changed contemporary lives and challenged the stability of modern societies. Based on preliminary findings and previous research, several similarities have been observed in the metaphorical representation of both migration and pandemics. In particular, three metaphorical mappings are commonly used to describe both migration and epidemics: water metaphors, fire metaphors, and war metaphors. Considering that human reasoning is intrinsically metaphorical and imaginative, and that abstract conceptual representations are grounded in sensorimotor systems, metaphors connect

these two realms by mapping the domain of familiar and concrete experience (the Source Domain) onto the domain of predominantly abstract and complex concepts (the Target Domain). This process enables a better understanding of the rich fabric of reality that surrounds us.

In this context, pandemics/illness and migration are subjective, sensitive experiences often conceptualized through metaphorical expressions. Given that Source/Target metaphorical mappings are systematic and tend to reproduce across similar situations, analyzing metaphors used to describe and conceptualize issues such as coronavirus and migration can reveal how Western society (in a broad sense) reacts and relates to crises through language.

Within this broader project, two aspects have been identified as areas requiring improvement and potential focus during the fellowship. The first concerns the methodology used to identify metaphors by implementing an approach based on Topic Modelling, which could significantly impact metaphor research in terms of the time and quantity of text analyzed. The second concerns the connection between literary texts and metaphors. Metaphors also serve a creative function and actively revive concepts. Literary writers can be seen as creators of metaphors, which gradually lose their metaphoricity and are adopted into ordinary language use. Therefore, focusing on literary texts may reveal whether some metaphorical mappings have emerged from literature and how their first occurrences were linguistically created.

Constanta Burlacu - Psalm 77 – Text Annotation and Linguistic Corpus Compilation for 16th Century Old Romanian

Areas such as digital critical editions, linguistic annotations, and compilation of (multi)linguistic corpora of old sources are completely undeveloped in Romanian Studies. The study of psalm 77 wants to bring an innovative approach to the field and be used as pilot study for the development of research aids to be employed for the study of old Romanian textual materials. The Psalm 77 project looks into the possibility of developing computational support for the linguistic analysis of old Romanian, that is, into the compilation of an annotated corpus of old Romanian texts. In particular, it wants to take into account the oldest textual sources of vernacular Romanian - religious texts mainly, translated from Church Slavonic. Within the timeframe of the project only psalm 77 will be looked at, as witnessed by seven 16th-century sources. The text will form the key core for devising a linguistic annotation tagset for old Romanian and is going to be the starting point for the compilation of a linguistic corpus for early vernacular Romanian. Based on the outcome of the Psalm 77 project, other textual sources of old Romanian will be annotated and integrated into the linguistic corpus.

Louis Burnard - Reviving the Victorian Plays Project

The project aims to investigate the feasibility of reviving and bringing up to date the Victorian Plays Project, currently hosted in Galway but apparently inactive since 2015. Its chief deliverable will be an enhanced digital catalogue, and an accompanying corpus, representing a major collection of English language dramatic texts from the Victorian period. The corpus will combine transcription and images of the Lacy's Acting Editions of Plays, as published between 1845 and 1870. It will be consistently and accurately encoded following the Guidelines of the TEI, as will the accompanying bibliographic and other descriptive metadata. It will be maintained as an open repository on GitHub, with all converted materials made available under a CC-BY licence. A further goal of the project will be to investigate and report on the applicability of “machine learning” techniques as a means of enhancing the performance of existing OCR platforms, to facilitate the automatic transformation of page images to structured transcripts, leveraging the information provided by the typography of this complex but highly conventionalised material. With the availability of a large and uniformly encoded corpus, the project will focus will shift to considerations and experiments showing how computational methods may invigorate the investigation of such topics as continuity and change in theatrical discourse, the emergence and mutation of dramatic stereotypes, or the mutual dependency of Victorian theatre and Victorian novel.

2nd call (18 April 2022 - 23 May 2022)

Cassandra Ulph - Developing attribute-based sentiment analysis model for Romantic-period letters

This project will address sentiments in relation to place (as pre-defined geographical entities and as more dynamic concepts) in the letters of Hester Piozzi, in particular her former home of Streatham Park. The pilot project, which this application forms part of, will be based on a corpus drawn from The Piozzi letters, the collected letters of Hester Thrale Piozzi from the period 1783-1821, in order to test and refine a dictionary for processing of sentiment analysis on the eighteenth-century private correspondence, which will in turn be applicable for a tool to other scholars. In the long term, this tool would form part of a larger application to digitise, transcribe in open-access format as an online edition, and analyse through computational methods the unpublished correspondence of Hester held in Special Collections at the University of Manchester.

Laura Soffiantini - Formulaic language in Latin funerary epigraphy

Formulaic language is a key aspect of Latin funerary texts. Ancient epitaphs tend to appear brief and repetitive, and their vast number presents complex challenges for scholars. From this perspective, a comprehensive overview of Latin funerary language remains lacking. Through the use of digital textual tools, this project aims to examine the presence of patterns in Latin formulae. Drawing on an existing dataset of 321,252 attestations of formulae extracted from a pool of 99,896 texts, the research will investigate the extent to which formulaic words form linguistic clusters rather than isolated units. By highlighting how the use of one formula may “activate” another, the study will reveal interconnections within funerary texts.

The next focus will be on the relationship between formulaic language and abbreviations. Using network analysis, the research will examine the degree to which formulaic sequences are abbreviated and how densely interconnected abbreviated and non-abbreviated formulae are. The combined objectives will allow for an in-depth investigation of shifts in formulaic clusters and contribute to understanding the structure of Latin funerary language.

Nisa Kirbač - Dead but Turkish: An NLP Analysis of the Obituaries of the Turkish Community in Belgium

This research project aims to analyse the content of both historical and contemporary obituaries of Turkish individuals based in Belgium using natural language processing (NLP) tools. The primary focus is on how national identity formation is reflected in these obituaries. The project involves the development of a multilingual corpus (Turkish, Dutch, and French) of death notices sourced from full-text newspaper archives and online platforms (e.g. Twitter). Additionally, a

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language model for the lesser-resourced language of Turkish will be developed to enable NLP-based analysis of the textual content.

Theodorus Fransen - From Modern to Early Irish: retrogressive diachronic morphological tagging methods and UD tagset interoperability solutions based on detailed linguistic analysis

The aim of this project is to work towards automated morphological tagging for Early Modern Irish (c. 1200–1650) and Early Irish (c. 600–1200), using the Universal Dependencies (UD) framework. A UD treebank does not yet exist for Early Modern Irish, and for Early Irish no tagger is available. The proposed methodology involves retrogressive diachronic morphological tagging methods based on a recently established Natural Language Processing pipeline using the UD framework; it produces good results for pre-standard Modern Irish texts going back as far as c. 1600.

This project will investigate, based on detailed linguistic analysis, how to further adapt this pipeline to successfully tag Early Modern Irish and Early Irish texts, representing increasingly more typologically different and morphologically complex language stages. The research will involve the creation and reuse of annotated datasets and the adaptation and interoperability of existing tagsets in line with UD guidelines. The project is envisaged to have many linguistic applications, not least in the field of corpus-based diachronic lexicography.

3rd call (7 November 2022 - 5 December 2022)

Federico Pianzola - Programmable corpora as linked data

The proposed project will conceptualize a data model that adapts the DraCor ontology to prose and fanfiction, and design an API that could feed the DraCor frontend and analytic tools starting from metadata in a triple store. By doing this, the DraCor infrastructure will be usable with corpora of derivative data stored in RDF format, thus extending the reusability and interoperability of this infrastructure.

Khanim Garayeva - Calculation of similarities or distances in Peter Ackroyd's historiographic metafiction and lexical diversity in Dan Brown's straightforward storytelling

Literary theoretician and Ackroyd scholar Susana Onega compares Peter Ackroyd's historiographic metafiction to North American "fabulation" and Spanish-American "magic realism." However, there are grounds for questioning this comparison, as Ackroyd's novels may not align closely with notions of 'realism.' To investigate this further, a reference corpus will be created, consisting of texts from the two aforementioned sub-genres, in order to calculate the similarities or distances between them and a primary corpus composed of Ackroyd's works.

Regarding the novels of Dan Brown, the study will focus on analyzing lexical diversity and tracking potential changes across his body of work—specifically, from his first novel to his most recent. Before attaining best-seller status, Brown had already been publishing fiction. This research will explore whether critical commentary on his writing style or the global reception of his later works contributed to any measurable transformation in his texts.

Lara Nagues - Building a digital corpus of vaudeville to study humour: issues and challenges

Building a digital corpus in order to be able to exploit it properly is a challenge in itself. How to select texts? Which data banks to use? Which OCR techniques to employ if the plain text is not directly accessible? What position should be taken with regard to the original text? Rather conservative, rather interventionist? And finally what level of granularity to choose when tagging in XML and according to which criteria? All these steps, because they are preliminary, are often quickly addressed in scientific works, whereas they are nevertheless fundamental. Indeed, the creation of a research object, whatever it may be, conditions the research itself and its results. This project proposes to examine all these questions through the construction of a digital corpus

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of the early nineteenth-century french vaudevilles, a kind of play mixed with song, with the longer-term objective of studying the humour present in their couplets.

Richard Zmelik - Building a literally corpus of 19th century Czech prose

The aim of the project is to build a digital corpus of 19th-century Czech prose that significantly thematizes the Prague environment. In addition to a database of digital literary maps, corpus mining tools form an integral part of the project. These tools include functions such as searching for specific word types according to morphological tags, word frequency analysis (type and token), and concordance searches. The corpus also features visualizations such as pie charts showing the percentage distribution of word types in each episode, word frequency lists, word clouds, sentiment analysis models, frequency models of narrative rhythms, and quantitative distributions of text segments (e.g. narrators, character speeches).

Participation in the CLS Fellowship at TCDH is intended to support the acquisition of new methods for machine-based text analysis and to explore further possibilities for developing software to support such work. The knowledge gained through the fellowship will be applied in subsequent phases of corpus development, ultimately aiming to support a more systematic understanding of literary processes related to the representation of Prague.

Roxana Patras - Criss-crossing Novel Illustrations and DALL-E generated Images: toward a data-rich ekphrasis

The project aims to bridge the latest technology (DALL-E image generator) with historical data: a. descriptive sequences of novels (faces and places); b. illustrations of novels.

Committed to supplementing the existing textual resources, the proposal also involves a reconsideration of the original artefact that is both timely and necessary in CLS: the legacy of textualism, which made text-processing prevail over image processing. At the same time, interest in images was spurred by the ascertainment that lesser-resourced languages are difficult to integrate into multilingual investigations unless they address universalia such as visual devices.

By data-rich ekphrasis is meant the output of the illustrating automaton when prompted with sequences of words and images linked in or belonging to the same plot: a machine replication of the reader's response to a set of textual and visual characteristics, aided by memory and engagement.

The exploration of ekphrasis here develops from the hypothesis that the illustrations of consumer novels are, like the texts themselves, aggregations of (visual) clichés. Thus, the confrontation of human illustrations and automatic illustrations (produced with DALL-E fed with description chunks) might shed light on the functionality of the cliché and of the ready-made sequences.

Jana-Katharina Mende - Monolingualism Deconstructed: Modelling Hidden and Invisible Multilingualism in German literature (1790-1890)

The current research project investigates approaches to a history of multilingual literature in the 19th century. While there is extensive research on multilingual literature in the 20th century as well as on pre-modern multilingualism, little is known about the fate of multilingualism during the period of language standardisation and unification in the 19th century. A new theoretical framework for a multilingual literary history in Europe is needed to address these gaps and to shift philological studies towards a modern and multilingual perspective on historical literary phenomena.

The project consists of three analytical levels, each leading to distinct outputs. First, a list of 19th-century multilingual writers—compiled using historical biographical and geographical data from German biographical dictionaries (Literaturlexika)—will illustrate the extent of multilingual literary activity during the period. Secondly, this database will form the basis of a core corpus consisting of texts produced by individuals active as writers in multilingual cities between 1790 and 1890.

Thirdly, case studies on selected literary networks in 19th-century multilingual centres—focusing on authors, genres, and text types—will explore the forms and functions of multilingualism. An initial case study on multilingual literary communities in Bratislava (Preßburg) has already produced promising results.

Maciej Maryl - Social Network Analysis of Career Trajectories in Polish Literature After 1989

The project aims to provide insights into literary reception of the Polish authors after the cultural transition of 1989 by applying social network analysis (SNA) methods to analyse relationships mined from bibliographical and textual data. The project will produce several case studies on the material derived from Polish Literary Bibliography (PBL) and the Corpus of Literary Discourse 1822-2022 (KDL). The case studies will employ network analysis and visualisation techniques to study the relationships between the actors of literary life and provide data-stories of career trajectories and success (or failure) patterns of particular writers (with a focus on Olga Tokarczuk).

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The project will focus on selected, diverse group of authors to produce data stories of their career trajectories. These will be presented as data stories based on mixed method approach to collected datasets: on the one hand it will take the advantage network statistics and visualisation of tendencies overtime (using Gephi and igraph) on the other, will use more advanced and qualitative queries to reveal overall patterns and outliers in data (with Neo4j).

4th call (2 May 2023 - 30 May 2023)

Ewa Data-Bukowska - The principle of sustainability as the basis for the translator's stylistic creation

The overarching objective of this project is to determine whether the Swedish translation of Witold Gombrowicz's unique novel *Trans-Atlantyck*, carried out by translator Anders Bodegård (first published in 2009), is based on a certain general principle that forms the foundation of the translator's stylistic creation and, consequently, a sense-making mechanism for multi-level readings of the novel within the foreign target culture—readings that may be seen as congruent with the ways in which the text is interpreted in the source culture.

The hypothesis proposed in the project is that the principle underlying the translator's stylistic creation of the Swedish text is sustainability—a cognitively economical principle deeply rooted in the functioning of natural language in communication. This refers to the archetypal concept of sustainability as conceived by Hans Carl von Carlowitz (1645–1714). In this view, the principle involves striking a balance between the lost (old) and the new at the level of linguistic structures. In the Swedish translation, this principle is evident both in the translator's adherence to Gombrowicz's own stylistic guidelines and in a creative approach to communication, particularly through the use of linguistic structures that can be considered progressive (new) in contemporary Swedish. The frequency and combinations of such structures, conceived at various linguistic levels, constitute patterns of expression that shape the linguistic construction of the translated text and its multifaceted style.

The research aims to identify these patterns and contextualize them in order to demonstrate the work's translatability at the stylistic level.

Wiktor Dziemski - Can't you see what I'm going through? Stylometrical analysis of Marcus Tullius Cicero's works in their correlation to the author's life

This project aims to study the correlation between the literary style of Marcus Tullius Cicero and the various events that occurred during his lifetime. Cicero, being one of the greatest Roman orators, writers, and philosophers, left a rich literary legacy consisting of speeches, philosophical treatises, and many personal letters exchanged with the most influential and remarkable men of his time. The exact chronology of most of these works is available, making it possible to associate each piece of Cicero's writing with a specific situation in his life.

The prolific Roman author experienced much during his lifetime. At the peak of his political career, he was elected consul and named *pater patriae* for saving Rome from an ongoing conspiracy. Later, however, he was sent into exile and even lost his house on the Palatine Hill.

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From his personal letters, it is known how deeply he mourned the death of his beloved daughter, Tullia.

The clear shift in Cicero's interests and the genres of his writings has been noted by scholars. This development, however, does not necessarily correspond to a change in the author's style and therefore requires further research.

Eduardo Fernández Guerrero - Distant reading of early modern prophecies across Europe: corpus formation and testing

This project proposes the creation of a proof of concept for a FAIR corpus of early modern Latin prophecies from the 16th century, exploring the hypothesis of their transnational nature. The primary objectives are to analyze the impact of socio-political contexts on prophetic literature, identify distinctive linguistic patterns and rhetorical devices, and examine how these texts differ from other genres. Drawing on expertise in prophetic discourse, classical philology, and digital humanities, the project will employ sentiment analysis and part-of-speech (POS) tagging to quantify shifts in emotional tone, mood, and grammatical structure.

The project will also address challenges related to intertextuality, corpus balancing, and the standardization of existing repositories. As a proof of concept carried out over a three-month period, the project will lay the groundwork for the potential development of a comprehensive corpus. The resulting insights will deepen understanding of the emotional and linguistic landscape of early modern prophetic literature, thereby shedding light on a significant yet often overlooked aspect of Western literary history.

Rocio Hernández-Arias - Digital Academic Edition of 'O anarquista' (1924), by Leandro Pita

The project "Digital Academic Edition of 'O anarquista' (1924), by Leandro Pita" is specifically related to the output of the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH). The Centre offers information and training in TEI annotation, which is the primary encoding language intended for application to the text cited below. With this background and the outcomes of the project, it will be possible to apply the acquired knowledge to other Anarchist texts currently under study. The ultimate goal is to create a Digital Library of Spanish Anarchism in the future, making the ability to digitally edit literary texts a key step in professional development. The final edition of 'O anarquista', written in the Galician language, will be accessible via the website of the Instituto da Lingua Galega (ILG). From this website, readers will be able to discover a forgotten text - an exceptional gem of the Galician anarchist movement.

Elisabeth Joyce - The New York School of Poetry: A distant reading of affinities

This fellowship will provide the tools and skills necessary to conduct a longer study on the New York School of Poets by integrating the distant readings of these analyses with a closer examination of what the distant readings point to. “Schools” of art are not identified entirely at random, but this project seeks to explore whether a system can be developed to measure relationships between groups of poems, in order to determine the extent to which the definition of a “school” is founded on anything more than a coincidence of similar dates and locations of the artists.

Jyothi Justin - Seeing the Unseen: Locating the Women of Independent India’s Unheard Dalit Massacres

The aim of the proposed project is to make use of feminist geocriticism to negate the absence of female narratives in Dalit massacres by placing them against the spaces that they occupy. This project looks at the spatial segregation of the Dalits (to the outskirts of villages) in India, to understand the possible relation between the spatial location of the Dalits and the violence against them. The study primarily looks at the interconnections between caste, space and gender in Dalit massacres. Therefore, the major research question of this study is: “Where are the women of independent India’s unheard Dalit Massacres?”.

The events chosen for this study includes: the Kilvenmani Massacre (1968, Tamil Nadu) and the Marichjhapi Massacre (1979, West Bengal). The primary aim of this study is to use technology to render the Dalit women of the selected massacres visible by developing a database of the real and fictional survivors of the massacres from different sources (fiction, films, newspaper reports, oral history, documentaries) and locating them on digital maps. The final interactive mapping visualization will contain information about the identified women in multimedia along with their narratives thereby serving as a (spatial) platform to organize and archive the same.

Natalia Kamovnikova - Corpus-building, classification, and preservation of contemporary anti-war poetry in the context of its electronic and social vulnerability

The project targets corpus-building and the systematization of rapidly emerging anti-war poetry and its translations. Recent military hostilities have sparked a surge in protest and anti-war literature. This body of work has reached an unprecedented scale and demonstrates high levels of poetic expressivity, yet it remains largely invisible to global readers due to geopolitical barriers and strict governmental control over digital content. Under such conditions, corpus-building is severely challenged, as the circulation of this poetry is confined to social networks and temporary websites.

The increase in political repression, arrests, and threats to personal safety has heightened the social, political, and physical vulnerability of poets who remain in affected regions. This

vulnerability has a direct impact on data storage and preservation: in life-threatening situations, webpages containing valuable poetic material may be deleted by authors or their families to protect themselves and their communities. In this context, corpus-building, systematization, and preservation of contemporary literary works require innovative approaches and methodologies. The application of modern digital tools and methods can offer solutions to linguistic and archival challenges that have been obstructed by non-linguistic factors.

Marko Milosev - Words to actions: How and if ideology translates to violence in the case of interwar fascist organizations

The current project examines how and whether fascist ideology translates into violent actions in real life. The case study focuses on several fascist movements during the interwar period. The analysis is conducted in two parts: first, factual data about violent incidents is gathered and mapped; second, this data is cross-referenced with fascist publications to track changes in the frequency of violent rhetoric and calls for harm. Given the large volume of data, a computational approach is employed, using natural language processing and machine learning. Source material is extracted using OCR (Tesseract) and mapped for specific language patterns and sentiments. The project is currently in its early stages.

Julia Neugarten - Catching Feelings: Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Fanfiction about Greek Myth

Fanfiction - stories inspired by existing stories, written by and for fans and published online for free - often revolves around emotional trajectories. Emotional highs and lows are frequently central to fanfiction plots. This focus on emotion makes fanfiction interesting to analyze with computational sentiment analysis methods.

The aim of 'Catching Feelings' is to apply aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) to a corpus of over 5.000 fanfiction-texts about Greek myth, as well as a corpus of reviews for those stories. This analysis fits within the PhD-project 'Anchoring and Innovating Classical Motifs in Fanfiction', which analyzes how source material from Greco-Roman Antiquity is transformed in contemporary online fanfiction.

Using ABSA, the aim is to answer the following research questions:

1. How does fanfiction present emotional engagement with Greek myth?
2. Which aspects of this source material are loved, enjoyed, and appreciated?

By approaching sentiment both as a property of texts and as a phenomenon that arises in the encounter between texts and readers, the project addresses an important theoretical matter for

the application of sentiment analysis to narrative: where does the emotional impact of a story reside? Can it be measured in the text itself, or is it located in reader responses?

Emrah Peksoy - Dictionary Building for Narrative Arc

Narratives are fundamental to human communication, providing frameworks for conveying meaning and shared perspectives. Understanding the structure and progression of narratives is crucial in various fields, including literary studies and computational analysis. This project proposes a comprehensive approach to automatically identify and analyze narrative progression in novels using a lexical-semantic based method. While existing approaches, such as hand-curated dictionaries to identify narrative arc, offer valuable insights, they often lack comprehensive coverage and fail to encompass all semantic aspects. By leveraging automated text analysis and computational tools, this project aims to develop a novel dictionary specifically focused on narrative arc elements, including staging, plot progression, and resolution. The project's innovative approach holds promise for quantifying narrative structure across diverse texts, contributing to the advancement of computational literary studies and enabling a deeper understanding of storytelling dynamics.

Levente Seláf - Comparative Analysis of Poetical Texts with Digital Tools

This research project is connected to an ambitious initiative led by numerous European scholars to facilitate the comparison of European poetic traditions. Following the completion of POSTDATA's ontology of European poetry, based on the Linked Open Data model, the current objective is to develop a new model for interlinking databases that share only a limited number of specific common patterns. Collaboration with local specialists in Madrid may support the achievement of interoperability among several tools originally designed for different corpora and according to varying scientific standards.

In Prague, support is sought for the development of a new morpho-syntactic analyzer intended for the analysis of early modern Hungarian poetry. This effort forms part of ongoing research focused on the creation of a new version of the *Répertoire de la poésie hongroise ancienne*, envisioned as a full-text database. A comparative study of Early Modern Hungarian and Czech poetic forms using digital tools is also planned.

Haimo Stierner - The clash of the modernists - Comparing the expressionist journal "Der Sturm" and the journal "Der Querschnitt" from the Weimar Republic

This research project combines computational literary studies (CLS), periodical studies, and Bourdieu's field theory to examine and compare the expressionist literary journal *Der Sturm* and the journal *Der Querschnitt* from the Weimar Republic, and thus from the era of New Objectivity.

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

The primary focus is on analyzing journal programmes, distinctive writing styles, emerging networks, and literary polemics found within these publications. The central research question is: to what extent can the conflict between Expressionism and New Objectivity in these literary journals - identified in previous research - be reconstructed using computational methods? The theoretical framework is based on the quantitatively grounded theory of the literary field developed by the French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu. The project also aims to demonstrate the applicability of Bourdieu's theory to CLS methodologies.

5th call (6 November 2023 - 4 December 2023)

Lisa Teichmann - Translational Trajectories of German Fiction in the German and Austrian National Libraries

Who are the most translated authors of German fiction represented in Germanophone national collections? This project aims to create an infrastructure for digital tools that will enable researchers to investigate translations using data from the German and Austrian National Libraries and to visualize literary exchanges, translation flows, and networks between Germanophone literary communities of writers, publishers, translators, and readers at large. As part of the PhD thesis "Mapping German Fiction in Translation in the German National Library Catalog (1980–2020)," a method was developed and deployed for identifying translations by searching the library catalog according to the original language—in this case, German. For the German National Library, the method achieved a high accuracy in identifying translations (see Teichmann 2022, 60–65); however, it has not yet been tested on other library data. Building on previous work, this project will develop and test a new method for extracting and visualizing translation data from the Austrian National Library. This research not only contributes to making this resource and its data more accessible, but also represents a first step toward building a data infrastructure that extends national and linguistic boundaries.

Simone Marcenaro - Harmonizing Artistry: exploring the collaboration between AI and human expertise in translating Galician-Portuguese Troubadour poetry (phase one)

This project delves into the translation complexities of Galician-Portuguese troubadour poetry from the 12th to 14th centuries, exploring the fusion of AI-driven translation and human expertise. Despite the surge in literary machine translation interest, medieval literature, especially Galician-Portuguese poetry, remains understudied in this domain. The project aims to address this gap, aiming to incorporate medieval literature into contemporary translation practices. The collaboration merges AI and human translators to navigate linguistic nuances, cultural depths, and formal structures specific to medieval texts. The research entails defining AI training methodologies, incorporating diverse machine learning tools, and curating a corpus for comprehensive AI model training. Key aspects encompass linguistic shifts between Old Galician-Portuguese and modern Galician or Portuguese, cultural and linguistic disparities inherent in medieval texts, biases impacting translations, preservation of formal structures, and handling semantic ambiguity in complex medieval Iberian poetry. This research phase aims to conduct rigorous comparative analyses between AI and human translations, offering insights into AI effectiveness within this poetic context. The subsequent phase aims to create a digital edition, contributing to Romance medieval studies and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration between Unimol and the Moore Institute.

Patricia Garcia - Graphs of the Social Networks of Spanish Women Writers of Irish Descent in the 18th Century

Several women writers of recognized prestige in Spain, born during the 18th century, had Irish ancestry and, in some cases, documented family and personal relationships that still connected them with their country of origin. The project proposes to explore, on the basis of the personal connections that can be traced through documents and literary-historical works, the different visualizations of their relationship graphs. The main hypothesis to be corroborated is whether the relationships that connected them with their country of origin supported the publication of their works and, in each particular case, whether this support may have been motivated by the aim of disseminating Enlightenment ideas.

Furthermore, the overall aim of the project is to validate the method of social network analysis in historical and philological research, as a method capable of yielding first-rate research information by showing in a visual and effective way the similarities or differences between the different cases studied. In principle, the project will begin with the figures of Margarita Hickey, Inés Joyes y Blake, and Cecilia Böhl de Faber y Ruiz de Larrea (Irish maternal grandmother).

Floriana Ceresato - The digital Franco-Italian "Anseïs de Carthage"

"Anseïs de Carthage" is a 13th-century *chanson de geste* that belongs to the *Cycle du Roi*. It recounts the story of Anseïs, Charlemagne's nephew, who becomes king of Spain after the battle of Roncesvalles.

The *chanson* is preserved in five manuscripts and six fragments. One branch of the *stemma codicum* of this epic poem is written in Franco-Italian. A preliminary study of the Franco-Italian "Anseïs de Carthage" has been conducted, including the presentation of a semi-diplomatic transcription of the text.

With the support of the CLS INFRA Fellowship Programme, the aim is to produce a digital edition and conduct a linguistic study of the Franco-Italian "Anseïs de Carthage", with the goal of publishing the research online.

Vladimir Polomac - Universal Dependencies for Old Serbian and Serbian Church Slavonic: Creating a training data set for lemmatization and morphosyntactic annotation using UDPipe

The recent development of the UDPipe tool enables users to do automatic lemmatization and morphosyntactic annotation for contemporary languages but also for many classical languages

D9.1 TNA report, including process documentation and impact analysis

(e.g. Ancient Greek, Paleo-Hebrew, Coptic, Gothic, Sanskrit, Latin), as well as for older versions of modern Indo-European languages (e.g. Old French).

In the case of older Slavic languages, UDPipe supports automatic text processing through models for Old Church Slavonic and Old East Slavic. Initial steps in automatic lemmatization and morphosyntactic annotation via UDPipe have also been recently undertaken for Old Czech.

The general aim of this project is to create an initial dataset to be used for training models for the automatic lemmatization and morphosyntactic annotation of the oldest preserved Serbian texts from the 12th and 13th centuries, using the UDPipe tool.

The specific objectives of the project include:

- a) defining principles for the lemmatization of Old Serbian and Serbian Church Slavonic texts;
- b) developing a set of tags for morphosyntactic annotation in accordance with the Universal Dependencies standards for Old Church Slavonic and modern Slavic languages;
- c) manually compiling an initial dataset for model training with UDPipe.

Anna Baryshnikova - Digital Analysis of the Baltic Germans' Monthly Newspaper "Baltische Briefe": Employing Named-Entity Recognition Methods and Historical GIS to Construct a Digital Map of the Most Significant Places in the Baltic Germans' Homeland

This research project navigates the historical landscape of the Baltic Germans through cutting-edge digital analysis techniques applied to their monthly newspaper, *Baltische Briefe*. Utilizing advanced tools such as SpaCy or NameTag for Named-Entity Recognition (NER), and QGIS alongside ArcGIS, the study aims to construct a comprehensive digital map highlighting pivotal locales within the Baltic Germans' homeland.

By employing NER tools, the research systematically identifies and categorizes entities - including individuals, locations, and events - from the newspaper's content, integrating this information into a spatial framework. The resulting digital map is expected to offer a nuanced and visually informative representation of key places in the Baltic Germans' historical experience.

This interdisciplinary approach not only showcases the potential of digital methodologies in extracting insights from historical texts but also contributes to a deeper understanding of the cultural, social, and historical dynamics of the Baltic Germans, emphasizing the spatial dimensions that influenced their collective identity. The research thus exemplifies the power of integrating digital tools with historical sources to uncover hidden narratives and geographical patterns within a community's history.

Szemes Botond - New Metrics for Computational Drama Analysis

In most cases, Computational Drama Analysis builds on character networks created based on co-occurrences within scenes of a play. Other approaches, which apply stricter conditions (e.g. an edge can only be created through direct interactions), rely on a similar concept when modeling relationships between characters.

However, it may also be insightful to adopt a different perspective on the system of relations in a drama. One such approach is to examine the flow of information between characters - that is, to determine who frequently introduces new concepts into the discourse and who tends to repeat others and maintain already established topics.

This information-theoretic framework can complement existing metrics and offer a new way of describing characters on a quantitative basis. Based on pairwise comparisons, it also allows for an alternative method of representing character networks.

The method is developed in collaboration with researchers in computational drama analysis, with results made available on the DraCor platform - primarily through the enrichment of TEI XML mark-up in selected corpora.

Lucas van der Deijl - Deploying DutchDraCor. Integrating 150 early modern Dutch plays (1550-1700) into the infrastructure of the Drama Corpora Project (DraCor)

Scholars of Dutch literature are currently retelling the history of early modern Dutch theatre. Recent research has moved away from the traditional focus on separate language fields and national frameworks, instead revealing the many exchanges of stories, characters, and literary models across linguistic and cultural borders.

The Drama Corpora Project (DraCor), a *programmable corpus* containing multilingual collections of plays developed at the University of Potsdam and the Freie Universität Berlin, has been a crucial catalyst in the emergence of this new paradigm in theatre history. As a standardised collection of thousands of TEI-encoded plays from multiple periods and language fields, it enables both longitudinal and cross-lingual comparisons of European literatures.

However, such computational comparisons are not yet possible for Dutch theatre, as no Dutch subcorpus is currently available in DraCor. To address this gap, an initial sample of 150 early modern Dutch plays is being integrated into the DraCor infrastructure, forming the foundation of *DutchDraCor*. In addition, a workflow is being developed to facilitate the integration of future corpora of Dutch plays, enabling the long-term expansion of Dutch material within DraCor.

Agnieszka Szulińska - Behind the scenes. Integrating TEI Panorama of Polish drama data into DraCor Programmable Corpora

The project establishes a pathway for data interoperability between two infrastructures for TEI editions: DraCor and TEI Panorama. Its aim is to prepare a pilot integration into DraCor of a TEI edition of the Polish Romantic drama *Samuel Zborowski* - a complex textual case involving an unfinished and unpublished manuscript existing in numerous versions, currently being edited by the TEI Panorama team.

The project will increase multilingualism of DraCor by initiating the first Polish-language collection, and enhance the reusability of data from the TEI Panorama platform in alignment with FAIR principles. In addition, a workflow is being developed to document the process of establishing interoperability between two infrastructures with differing TEI implementations - offering broader benefits to the digital scholarly editions community.

Radim Hladík - A sprint for FAIRer data: Development of features for data exchange and publication in research software for qualitative data analysis

The reQual package, licensed under the MIT license, is a software application committed to the principles of Open Science, Open Source, and Open Data. The proposed development aims to improve the handling of text data in the reQual application, making it easier to share and reuse. The goal is to enhance the openness of the software and increase its capacity to handle data according to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. Two specific features are proposed: 1) import and export of data based on the REFI-QDA exchange format using XML, which has been established as a standard in qualitative data analysis; 2) anonymization of data to improve the culture of data sharing in qualitative data analysis. The Trier Center for Digital Humanities (TCDH) is an optimal host for this project due to its commitment to similar principles and its expertise in research software development.

Kim Byungjun - Integrative Approaches in Computational Literary Studies and Global Knowledge Structures

This project aims to innovate and enhance Computational Literary Studies (CLS) at the Trier Center for Digital Humanities (TCDH) through the integration of advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) methodologies and bibliometric analysis of global academic databases. The focus is on applying specialized NLP techniques - such as topic modeling, dynamic word embedding, and emotion classification - to existing CLS projects at TCDH. Extensive experience in utilizing these techniques in diverse research contexts supports the potential to significantly enrich the center's ongoing projects.

Complementing this is bibliometrics-based research, which originated from a doctoral thesis examining the knowledge structure of Korean humanities through an analysis of 250,000 papers from the Korea Citation Index (KCI). This study is currently being expanded to incorporate

OpenAlex, the world's most extensive open academic database. The expansion aims to compare and contrast knowledge structures in Korea with those globally, focusing on Europe, North America, and Asia. This twofold approach promises to contribute to methodological advancement in CLS and offers a unique opportunity to explore the global distribution and structure of academic disciplines, thereby enriching the academic database research landscape at TCDH.

Rozalia Słodczyk - Operationalising the nocturne genre – comparative traditional and digital humanities research using i.a. topic modeling on the example of contemporary Polish and Italian poetry

The research project centers on the analysis of the nocturne genre within contemporary Polish and Italian poetry, using a computational approach - specifically topic modeling - as an alternative to traditional genre understanding. Conducted on a self-prepared corpus of Polish and Italian contemporary poetry, the project encompasses a wide range of authors, including both well-known and emerging voices, representing different historical moments as well as literary trends. The study's focus on less-researched "smaller genres," and specifically "cross-domain genres" (of which the nocturne is an example) within poetry raises questions about, among other things, the thematic and stylistic determinants shaping these genres in synchronic and diachronic terms. Employing macroanalysis methods, the study aims to compare algorithmic findings with philological interpretations.

Methodologically, various techniques such as topic modeling, stylometric analysis, and sentiment detection are used to classify and quantify the thematic aspects of the nocturne. The ultimate goal is to create a computational model defining nocturnal texts through quantifiable linguistic features. By means of comparative methods, combining the results of close and distant reading, the research intends to contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the nocturne genre and its significance across different authors, periods, and languages. The objective is to unveil the nocturne's characteristics and variations, relating to associations with specific themes, motifs, stylistic features, and determinants of place and time.

6th call (June 2025 - November 2025, rolling call)

Alyaxey Yaskevich - Exploring classical Belarusian fiction with the methods of corpus and computational linguistics

The project involves compiling a corpus of classical Belarusian fiction and analysing its content across several dimensions, including language shift, changes in the use of named entities, and stylistic variation. The goal is not only to address a number of research questions but also to publish the corpus and promote Belarusian literature - a little-studied topic - for further research by a wider audience.

Anna Medrzecka - Polish poetry corpus: creation, integration with PoeTree, computational poetics

The project aims to enhance and integrate a comprehensive corpus of Polish poetry into the multilingual PoeTree corpus, facilitating advanced computational studies in poetics. The primary objectives are threefold: first, to expand an annotated corpus of Polish poetry in collaboration with CLARIN-PL; second, to integrate this corpus seamlessly into PoeTree, which currently includes over 330,000 poems across ten languages but lacks Polish poetry; and third, to conduct pilot studies on versology using the integrated corpus.

The project will involve creating a balanced dataset from various sources, annotating and enriching the texts, and conducting preliminary analyses of rhyme and verse patterns. The ultimate goal is to establish a resource that supports large-scale comparative and computational research, contributing significantly to Polish poetic studies and the broader field of digital literary studies.

Collaboration with experts at Charles University and the Institute of Czech Literature will ensure efficient progress and impactful outcomes. The project aligns with CLS INFRA's mission by developing high-quality scholarly resources, promoting open communication, and advancing the infrastructure for literary research.

Kathryn Laing, Geraldine Brassil - Enhancing the Irish Women's Writing Network 1880-1920 Website: Data Capture, Digitisation, Visualisation

The Irish Women's Writing (1880–1920) Network (IWWN) was founded in 2016 with the aim of bringing together international scholars in this field. The aim of the proposed research project is for IWWN Team members to acquire the tools to enhance the digital capacity of the IWWN website, a WordPress site established with the launch of the Network. The development of the website has been collaborative, with Network Team members giving freely of time and intellectual labour. Digital expertise is crucial however in realising ambitions to create not only a networking, information sharing site, but a digital repository that facilitates access to out-of-print materials, accumulated data, and other forms of scholarly knowledge. Aligned with this objective

the project includes excel datasets which record Irish women writers across a sample number of nineteenth-century periodicals. Notable is their capacity for expansion. The aim is that the data will be deposited in a suitable repository, making it a searchable, stable, open access resource, while at the same time protecting the integrity of the database. As a test-case for future endeavours, the project will explore possibilities for developing the Network website itself as a repository for this and other related datasets.

Maria-Corina Dimitiru - Parametrization Guidelines in StyloR for the Romanian Language

The project aims to propose a set of tasks for testing the performance of the StyloR package for intuitive users when applied to Romanian, in order to enhance the efficiency of further research in this field. A corpus consisting of 123 Romanian popular novels published between 1850 and 1920 will be used, five of which were written by anonymous authors. Cluster Analysis, Bootstrap Consensus Tree, and Principal Components Analysis will be applied to the corpus, varying different parameters in each case. As the StyloR package has been little used on Romanian texts to date, and since no consensus has yet been reached on the optimal parameters for specific research objectives, multiple combinations of parameters will be tested to determine which most closely align with existing information provided by literary histories concerning authorship attribution, language period, subgenre, and gender categorisation.

Mercedes de Luis Andrès - Book Clubs in Journalism Culture – BoJo Club

BoJo Club embarks on a journey through communication rituals to unveil the transformative power of reading in book clubs within journalism communities. Transcending disciplinary boundaries, these book clubs reveal themselves as promising communication ecosystems. The case studies are catalogued through the lens of a social constructivist framework and mapped globally. From a book club at a public radio station maintained by an avid reader in Oregon to a community platform in Bogotá created by a journalist that shares Colombian literature, to an environmental book club nurtured by journalists in Madrid, or a New York club focused on history books that challenge censorship, the BoJo Club research reveals echoes of the first literary salons, standing on the shoulders of giants. By applying distant reading techniques, new patterns emerge that may not be apparent through close reading alone. Understanding reading circles in journalism worldwide, rather than isolated books, offers hidden insights among reading societies. The BoJo Club collection is built as an open library in a digital catalogue. These books maintain interest beyond their value as literary works. May the power of these readings foster empathy, well-being, and communal bonds?

Ewa Data-Bukowska - What characterizes the Polish novel *Trans-Atlantyk* by W. Gombrowicz is unconventional syntax. Does the Swedish translation of the novel preserve the syntactic unconventionality? How can we measure that?

The overarching objective of the project is to determine whether the Swedish translation of Witold Gombrowicz's unique novel *Trans-Atlantyk*, produced by the translator Anders Bodegård (first published in 2009), is based on a general principle that serves as the foundation for the translator's stylistic choices and, consequently, as a mechanism enabling multi-level interpretations of the novel within the context of the foreign target culture - interpretations that may be seen as congruent with those in the source culture.

The hypothesis advanced in the project is that the translator's stylistic creation of the Swedish text is guided by the principle of sustainability—a cognitively economical concept deeply embedded in the function of natural language in communication. This principle draws upon the archetypal idea of sustainability as formulated by Hans Carl von Carlowitz (1645–1714). Within this framework, sustainability entails a balance between what is lost (the old) and what is introduced (the new) at the level of linguistic structure.

In the Swedish translation, this principle manifests both in adherence to Gombrowicz's own stylistic guidelines and in the translator's creative communicative strategies, particularly through the use of linguistic structures that may now be regarded as progressive or innovative within Swedish. The frequency and combination of such structures, formed across different linguistic levels, constitute expression patterns that underlie the construction of the translated text and its multifaceted stylistic character.

The aim of the research is to identify these patterns and to contextualise them in order to demonstrate the translatability of the work at the level of style.

Annex II – Resources

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